

Dipolar Cycloaddition Reactions of some Nickel(II) and Palladium(II) Azido Complexes

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Azido complexes of the types $NiL^{1-3}N_3$, $PdL^{1-3}N_3$ and $[L^1Ni-N_3-NiL^1]ClO_4$, where the principal ligands HL^{1-3} contain N,S donor units, undergo facile 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reactions with aliphatic and aromatic nitriles, alkenes, alkynes, phenylisothiocyanate and carbon disulphide. In all cases the products have been isolated in high yield. From extensive kinetic studies the following order of reactions have been noted, alkynes > nitriles >> alkenes. The activation of azido group is dependent upon the nature of associated ligand L; the reaction rate decreases with the increase of σ -donor capacity of L. Palladium(II) complexes are less active than the nickel(II) analogues because of decreased charge density of the metal ion. The rate constants of cycloaddition reactions increase with reactants carrying electron withdrawing group, and in the case of aromatic nitriles Hammett correlation has been obtained. The mechanism of reaction has been discussed in the light of thermodynamic parameters of activated state.

DIPOLAR cycloaddition reactions have emerged as powerful aids for synthesising organic molecules¹⁻⁵. Of particular importance is the 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition in which a 1,3-dipolar molecule capable of existing in zwitterionic resonance structures, can add on to a multiple bonded system, the dipolarophile. 1,3-Dipoles can be either propargylallenyl type or allyl type. In terms of valence-bond description, coordinated azide can be represented by two canonical forms,

which belong to the propargylallenyl type, and thus capable of undergoing 1,3-cycloaddition reactions. Because a variety of otherwise inaccessible metal bound heterocyclic molecules can be generated, such studies are of growing importance in the area of coordination chemistry⁶⁻¹². We provide here an overview of our recent studies on end-on (1) and end-to-end (2) linked azido complexes of nickel(II) and palladium(II), detail of which will be published elsewhere.

The formation of precursor azido complexes 1 and 2 from monoprotic tridentate ligands (HL^{1-3}) are shown in Scheme 1. These compounds undergo facile cycloaddition reactions with aliphatic and aromatic nitriles to form tetrazolate complexes. Similar reactions with alkenes, e.g. dimethylfumarate and acrylonitrile result in the formation of triazolinate complexes. Alkynes, such as dimethylacetylenedicarboxylate and dibenzoylacetylene react very easily to form triazolinate complexes. Heterocumulenes, such as carbon disulphide and phenylisothiocyanate react smoothly to produce thiotriazolinate and tetrazolinthionate complexes, respectively. The thiotriazolinate complexes being thermally less stable are converted to isothiocyanato

Scheme 1

complexes on prolonged boiling. The reactions undergone by complexes 1 and 2 are depicted in Schemes 2 and 3, respectively.

The cycloaddition reactions could be followed easily from their infrared spectra by the disappearance of $\nu_{as}(N_3)$ vibrations at ~ 2050 (1) and 2090 cm^{-1} (2), and the appearance of several new bands in the range $1250-750\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to the heterocyclic rings. The electronic spectra of the nickel(II) complexes also show considerable shift of the d-d band ($\sim 18000\text{ cm}^{-1}$) to a higher energy relative to that of the azido complexes ($\sim 16000\text{ cm}^{-1}$), and served as the basis of kinetic studies. In the palladium(II) complexes, bands due to d-d transition could not be located as these are buried under CT as well as ligand originated $\pi-\pi^*$

Scheme 2

Scheme 3

transitions. As expected, the compounds derived from **1** are non-electrolytes, whereas those from **2** are 1 : 1 electrolytes. All of the complexes under consideration have square-planar steric environment.

¹H nmr spectra of these compounds have provided useful information concerning stereochemistry and nature of metal-ligand bonding. Detail consideration of these spectra cannot be made here. It would be suffice to say that the resultant heterocyclic rings being ambidentate in nature, can bind metal atoms either through N¹- or N²- nitrogen atoms. The occurrence of N¹- or N²-isomer, or a mixture of both will depend upon the nature of heterocyclic ring substituents. Construction of molecular models reveal that in the case of N¹-isomer both *syn*- and *anti*-stereoisomers can result as a consequence of steric involvement. In fact, the CH₃ resonances of the triazolone complexes formed by reacting ML¹N₂ with CH₃CN show the existence of all three isomers. It is possible to distinguish between the N¹- and N²-isomers of triazolone complexes by considering the fact that the chemical shifts of the substituents will be different for N¹-, but same for N²-isomer. Table 1 summarises the results obtained for a few representative compounds.

Kinetics and mechanism of cycloaddition reactions have been investigated in detail by varying the substrate (*i.e.* **1** and **2**), reactant (dipolarophile), solvent (NO₂Ph, NO₂Me, DMF) and temperature (40-70°). The question whether these reactions take place in a stepwise or in a concerted way can be decided by taking into consideration the thermodynamic parameters of the activated state and solvent effect. Concerted reactions require¹ a high degree of order in the transition state, *i.e.* at the peak of the activation barrier the reactants must be precisely aligned with respect to each other. This means that in a concerted process there will be large negative entropies of activation (ΔS^{*}) and only moderate enthalpy (ΔH^{*}) changes. The results given in Table 2 correspond to the above requirements. Moreover, as expected¹, the variation of solvents do not affect the reaction rates significantly.

The mechanism of cycloaddition reaction with organic nitriles and the formation of N¹- and N²-isomers can be reconciled by considering prior coordination of the nitrile to the metal ion and the formation of a three-membered activated complex^{1,2} (Scheme 4). Obviously, the N¹-isomer will predominate with R acting as a electron-releasing group (*e.g.* Me) and reverse with R, an electron-withdrawing substituent (*e.g.* *p*-NO₂C₆H₄).

The dependence of rate constants on the polarisation of dipolarophile has been observed by using various *para*-substituted benzonitriles. As the electron withdrawing ability of the *para*-substituent increases, enhancement of reaction rate occurs. This has become clearly evident by observing nice Hammett correlation using various nitriles and substrates in different solvent medium. Concerning

TABLE 1—CHEMICAL SHIFTS OF HETEROCYCLIC RINGS IN THE CYCLOADDITION PRODUCTS

Complex	Reactant	δ	Remarks
NiL ¹ N ₂	CH ₃ CN	OH ₂ : 2.58(s), 2.66(s), 2.78(s)	{ N ² -isomer, and N ¹ -isomer in syn and anti form
PdL ¹ N ₂	CH ₃ CN	OH ₂ : 2.32(s), 2.58(s), 2.68(s)	
NiL ¹ N ₂	p-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CN	C ₆ H ₄ : 8.35(m)	N ² -isomer
NiL ¹ N ₂	H ₂ CO ₂ CHO=CHCO ₂ CH ₃	CO ₂ CH ₃ : 3.86(s),	N ² -isomer
		CH=OH : 4.0(s), 4.12(s)	N ² -isomer
PdL ¹ N ₂	H ₂ CO ₂ CO≡COO ₂ CH ₃	CO ₂ CH ₃ : 3.82(s)	N ² -isomer
NiL ¹ N ₂	C ₆ H ₅ NCS	C ₆ H ₅ : 7.78(m)	

TABLE 2—KINETIC DATA FOR CYCLOADDITION REACTIONS IN NITROBENZENE

Complex	Reactant	k 50° × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	ΔH [‡] kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔS [‡] kcal mol ⁻¹
NiL ¹ N ₂	p-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CN	3.05	12	-24
NiL ¹ N ₂	p-ClO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CN	0.27		
NiL ¹ N ₂	C ₆ H ₅ CN	0.09		
NiL ² N ₂	p-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CN	2.37	14	-21
NiL ² N ₂	p-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CN	0.63	16	-17
NiL ² N ₂	H ₂ CO ₂ C≡CCO ₂ CH ₃	35.2	10	-28
NiL ² N ₂	C ₆ H ₅ COO≡COO ₂ C ₆ H ₅	75*	6	-36

* At 30°.

Scheme 4

the rate of reactions with different type of dipolarophiles the following reactivity order has been noted, alkyne > nitrile >> alkene. Between the two alkyne derivatives used, dibenzoylacetylene is considerably more reactive than dimethylacetylenedicarboxylate. Here also, the difference arises due to stronger electron withdrawing power of the dibenzoyl group. In general, the rate constants for cycloaddition reactions of bridged azido complexes are less than that of the corresponding end-on variety. This is expected because the reaction rate depends to a great extent upon the charge separation of 1,3-dipoles. In bridged azido complexes, the charge separation is less because the two ends of the azido group are connected to two same units.

From kinetic studies it has turned out that the reaction rates are also governed by the ligand unit present. With any particular dipolarophile the rate constants decrease in the order, L¹ (R=H) > L² (R=Me) > L³ (R=Et) which actually is the increased

order of the electron-releasing capacity of the substituents. It has also been observed that the palladium(II) complexes are less reactive toward cycloaddition reactions than their nickel(II) analogues. Evidently, this is due to greater charge density of Ni^{II} ion which in turn augments charge separation in azide. Table 2 provides relevant kinetic parameters for a few systems.

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